

Occurrence of Rhazine in *Hunteria corymbosa* Roxb. and its Biogenetic Correlation with Corymine

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*Hunteria corymbosa*¹ Roxb. (Sym. *Hunteria zeylanica* (Retz.) Gard. ex Thw. Fam : Apocynaceae) is a tall tree growing abundantly in the Coromandel coast, Tinnevely Ghats and Courtallum of Deccan Peninsula. The leaves of this plant are reported to contain corymine²(1) in fairly good proportion (0.6%). From the leaves of an Indian variety of *H. corymbosa* we could, however, obtain no corymine. Instead, our chemical investigation resulted in the isolation (0.03%) of a different alkaloid, C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₃, m. p. 234-36° (dec.), [α]_D ± 0° (CHCl₃) crystallised from a mixture of benzene-chloroform (1:1) in fine flakes. The alkaloidal colour reactions (conc. HNO₃→yellow; Hopkins-Cole→violet; Fröhde's reagent→navy blue; ceric ammonium sulphate→light yellow), the ultraviolet [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 227, 280 and 290 mμ(log ε, 4.51, 3.83 and 3.72)] and infrared [ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3322, 2941 and 1725 cm⁻¹] absorptions in conjunction with other physical properties suggest its identity with rhazine (11),^{3,4} one of the major alkaloids of *Rhazya stricta* Decaisne. This has been finally confirmed by thin-layer chromatographic comparison, mixture m. p. determination of the base with an authentic sample of rhazine and also from their superimposable I.R spectra and those of their derivatives, the monomethiodide, C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₃.CH₃I, m.p. 220-22° (dec.) and the monoacetate, C₂₃H₂₆N₂O₄, m. p. 256-57° (dec.).

The occurrence of corymine and rhazine in the same plant species has a significant biogenetic implication. Although it has recently been proved that indole alkaloids of C₁₉–C₂₀ series originate by the combination of tryptophan and a cyclopentanoid monoterpene unit^{5,6} or their appropriate biochemical equivalents, we have reasons to believe that there are several indole bases for the genesis of which the above fundamental units are not possibly the direct precursors. Instead, these alkaloids are plausibly formed through the participation of preformed C₁₉–indole

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alkaloid intermediate^{7, 8} which may undergo various transformations giving rise to C₁₉-indolic bases of different skeleta. Thus, in the case of corymine and rhazine we may reasonably assume the corynanthenoid precursor (III) as a possible intermediate. Formation of bond between C-16 and C-5 or C-7 followed by appropriate biological sequence could lead to the formation of rhazine or corymine (Chart - I). Although no corynanthenoid alkaloid could be isolated from *H. corymbosa* as

yet, occurrence of such alkaloids in other *Hunteria* species^{9, 10} provides tangential evidence in support of the above contention. The preferential formation of rhazine over corymine and vice-versa in *H. corymbosa* of different origin is possibly due to ecological variation which may influence the activity of the enzymes—the latter governing the biological processes leading to the complete synthesis of the alkaloids.

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